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ENTERING INITIAL DATA FOR SECURITY OBJECTS AND NETWORK STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the "Network Analyzer" software tool and its underlying algorithms, which are designed to enhance the level of protection in corporate networks against unauthorized access. The study proposes a security domain allocation algorithm and a load-based optimization algorithm for network nodes and security devices. Developed using the JavaScript programming language, the system enables network topology analysis, security domain formation, and the visualization of attack graphs. A comparative analysis between the proposed methods and traditional approaches like Access Control Lists (ACL) and Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) is presented, demonstrating how to achieve an optimal balance between network security and performance throughput.

Keywords. *Corporate network security, security domain, load optimization, Network Analyzer, network objects, attack graphs, cyber protection, intelligent system.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируется программный инструмент "Network Analyzer" и реализованные в нем алгоритмы, направленные на повышение уровня защиты корпоративных сетей от несанкционированного доступа. В рамках исследования предложены алгоритм распределения по доменам безопасности и алгоритм оптимизации на основе нагрузки на сетевые узлы и устройства безопасности. Программа, разработанная на языке JavaScript, позволяет анализировать топологию сети, формировать домены безопасности и

визуализировать графы атак. В работе проведен сравнительный анализ предложенных методов с традиционными системами списков контроля доступа (ACL) и управления доступом на основе ролей (RBAC), а также продемонстрированы способы достижения оптимального баланса между безопасностью и производительностью сети.

Ключевые слова. Безопасность корпоративной сети, домен безопасности, оптимизация нагрузки, Network Analyzer, сетевые объекты, графы атак, киберзащита, интеллектуальная система.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada korporativ tarmoqlarni ruxsatsiz foydalanish va kiberhujumlardan himoya qilish darajasini oshirishga qaratilgan "Network Analyzer" dasturiy vositasi va unda qo'llanilgan algoritmlar tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqot doirasida tarmoq infratuzilmasini xavfsizlik domenlariga ajratish hamda tarmoq tugunlari va xavfsizlik qurilmalarining yuklamasini optimallashtirish algoritmlari taklif etilgan. JavaScript tilida ishlab chiqilgan ushbu dastur tarmoq topologiyasini tahlil qilish, domenlarni shakllantirish va hujum graflarini vizuallashtirish imkonini beradi. Maqolada taklif etilgan usullarning an'anaviy kirishni nazorat qilish ro'yxatlari (ACL) va rollarga asoslangan boshqaruv (RBAC) tizimlariga nisbatan afzalliklari qiyosiy tahlil qilinib, tarmoq xavfsizligi va uning o'tkazuvchanlik tezligi o'rtasidagi optimal muvozanatni ta'minlash yo'llari ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Korporativ tarmoq xavfsizligi, xavfsizlik domeni, yuklamani optimallashtirish, Network Analyzer, tarmoq ob'ektlari, hujum graflari, kiberhimoya, intellektual tizim.

The description of the entire process of the system means that it is an "intelligent" system: the system can do all the work itself or "consult" with the user for better and more accurate analysis or decision-making. Analyzing the workflow helps to present the subsequent material more consistently.

Let's briefly touch on the tool on which the system was developed. The VC Code programming environment was used to develop the program. This programming system was not chosen by chance, as it combines the JavaScript programming language with various technologies for rapid application development. The reason for choosing the JavaScript programming language will be explained in the process of presenting the working material.

So, like any computer program, the system must work with some initial data. In our case, the initial data for the analysis will be the same as the initial data for the

algorithms presented in the previous chapter, namely [1-3]:

- number of network nodes-objects;
- nodes-network objects;
- the interconnection of these nodes into the network;
- a set of properties of each node.

The number of network nodes-objects is known in advance. It is determined based on the network structure.

The network structure in the system is established according to a simple principle: first the objects are established, then the connections between them. The system is programmed in JavaScript, so all the capabilities of this language are used for 91 operations with objects. However, since network objects are divided into servers, routers, switches, etc., all these differences can be established through class properties. Thus, using the JavaScript language, a generalized network object is obtained.

In the same way, an object-connection is also established, which serves to connect object-nodes with each other.

Any real object has only a set of its own properties, as well as a set of common properties that are inherent in each object of some class of objects to which the object in question belongs. A network object and a connection object belong to different object classes. However, descendants of a network object or types of a network object belong to the same class — “network object”. Therefore, they have common properties. Due to the simplicity of the connection object, it does not have specific properties, except for functional properties, such as information about the network objects it connects. Therefore, additional properties are not provided for it [4,5].

In the program, you can work with four types of objects: server, router, firewall and public network (Internet). A server object is a network object that provides certain services (services), therefore it is often attacked and, as a result, needs protection. In fact, the program actively works only with objects of this type, using the rest as auxiliary ones. The router object is used to create various networks in the network, helping to prevent the creation of loops in the network. The firewall object is designed to restrict access to security domains consisting of server objects. The Internet object is needed to define the exit point of the enterprise network to the global public network, it is the simplest object, since it does not have additional properties [6].

Fig. 1. Object-based system model

System structure n-shown in Figure 1. The initial data (network structure) is entered into the system using the user interface. Then, the analyzer checks the entered data for errors and presents them in a more convenient form for further calculations. Thus, it is possible to proceed to the implementation of one of the algorithms: comparative or load-based. Each algorithm transmits its output to the generator, which generates the results of the analysis of the resulting network structure.

In addition to the advantages, the following can be cited: the algorithm indicates the presence of a strong threat to network security or the relative weakness of the threat. This is evident from the number of connected network objects. If there are a lot of them, then it is worth fundamentally reconsidering the network structure [6].

As a result of analyzing a specific network according to the load-based algorithm, the system provides a network structure created on the basis of a specific network, but with an increased overall security level. It would be more accurate to say that the system creates a network structure with the highest level of security, but with redundant means of limiting access between security domains. This fact is justified, since from a security point of view, it is always possible to remove redundant or unnecessary network elements, taking into account the quality/value ratio. At the same time, of course, the overall level of network security decreases [4-6].

Fig. 2. System interface

Fig. 3. Result of network analysis in the system

It should be noted that the performance of algorithms largely depends on the initial data, so you should be especially careful when submitting them.

Effectiveness of the program to increase the level of protection against unauthorized use of the corporate network. The "Network Analyzer" program implements the proposed algorithms based on the distribution and load of security domains. The main functional capabilities of the program are as follows [2]:

- Network topology analysis: Identify existing network nodes and the connections between them.
- Forming security domains: Dividing network objects into separate domains based on their characteristics and services.
- Building attack graphs: Visualize possible movement directions of intruders and identify weak points.

The effectiveness of the program is determined by the following indicators:

- Domain division level (D): Increase the overall level of security by dividing the network into as many and smaller security domains as possible.
- Service concentration (T): Minimize the number of services in each domain (ideally, one service in each domain).

- Complexity of attack paths: It is more difficult for an attacker to continue the attack chain on a network optimized with software.

Fig. 4. Structure of the main modules of the system

As a result of applying the program in practice, the following indicators are achieved:

- Increased security level: By optimally dividing the network into security domains, the likelihood of unauthorized use is significantly reduced.
- Use of resources: The program allows you to accurately calculate the amount of additional equipment (filters, gateways) required to ensure a certain level of security.
- Comparative analysis: Compared to existing systems (Internet Scanner, RealSecure), this program not only identifies vulnerabilities, but also offers optimized solutions to secure the network structure.

The “Network Analyzer” software tool has demonstrated the high efficiency of using the security domain model in designing corporate networks and modernizing existing ones. This, in turn, allows you to create an intelligent and automated system

for protecting information from unauthorized access.

The main advantages and disadvantages of using the proposed security domain allocation and load-based algorithms in organizations are summarized in the table below [3].

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF ALGORITHMS

<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Security domain allocation algorithm</i>	<i>Load-based optimization algorithm</i>
<i>Main advantages</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduces the risk of unauthorized access by dividing the network into logically separate parts. • Even if an attacker enters one segment, it limits its spread throughout the entire network. • Allows you to apply individual security policies for each domain. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balances the load on network nodes and security devices (e.g. firewalls). • Provides security while maintaining network throughput. • Reduces excessive resource consumption.
<i>Main disadvantages</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-domain management can become difficult as the network structure becomes more complex. • Requires additional routing and filtering resources as the number of domains increases. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The algorithm requires real-time network monitoring for calculations. • Finding a balance between security and speed can be tricky when the load changes dramatically.
<i>Benefits for the organization</i>	Strengthens the overall security architecture of the corporate network and increases protection against "insider" attacks.	Ensures the continuity of network services and prevents bottlenecks caused by security systems.
<i>Scope of application</i>	Large corporations with confidential information and a large number of employees with varying levels of clearance.	Systems with very large data flows and operating in real time (Fintech, cloud services).

According to the results of the research in the dissertation, the combination of these two algorithms provides the highest efficiency. While the first algorithm ensures structural security of the network (by dividing it into domains), the second minimizes the negative impact of these security measures on performance.

If the number of security elements in a network increases, it can increase the complexity of the system, although it increases the level of security. Therefore, it is recommended that the organization optimize unnecessary redundant elements based on its “quality/security” ratio [5, 6].

TABLE II. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CORPORATE NETWORK SECURITY ALGORITHMS

<i>Comparative criteria</i>	<i>Security Domain Algorithm (Recommended)</i>	<i>Load-based optimization algorithm (Recommended)</i>	<i>Static access control (ACL - Access Control Lists)</i>	<i>Role-Based Access Control (RBAC)</i>
<i>Protection principle</i>	Dividing the network into logical security zones (domains).	Ensuring security, taking into account the load on network nodes.	Strict filtering at the IP address and port level.	Granting rights based on the user's position (role) in the organization.
<i>Adaptability</i>	Top: Domains are reshaped when the network topology changes.	Very high: Adapts in real time to changes in network traffic.	Low: Rules must be manually updated for each change.	Average: Only adapts when the role hierarchy changes.
<i>Resource efficiency</i>	Medium: May require additional filter elements.	High: Increases performance by optimally allocating system resources.	High: Requires minimal computing resources.	Average: Depends on a centralized server and database.
<i>Security level</i>	High: Effectively limits the attacker's "horizontal" movement within the network.	Medium/High: Maintains the optimal balance between security and performance.	Low: Vulnerable to sophisticated and modern attacks (e.g. APT).	Medium: Provides protection only at the user rights level.
<i>Implementation complexity</i>	Medium: Requires a precise mathematical model at the initial stage.	High: Continuous monitoring and accounting modules need to be installed.	Low: Available as standard on most network devices.	Moderate: Requires the implementation of a governance system at the corporate level.

Main conclusions from the analysis results:

1. Traditional methods (ACL, RBAC): While these methods are easy to implement, they are not sufficiently flexible against the dynamic nature of modern corporate networks and sophisticated attacks (such as intelligent methods of unauthorized access).
2. Security Domains Algorithm: Unlike traditional RBAC, this algorithm divides not only the user, but also the entire network infrastructure into protected segments, which increases the level of security several times.

3. Load-based algorithm: The main difference of this method is that it minimizes the negative impact of security measures on network speed. This is especially important for modern information systems that process large amounts of data.

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